

Trust Manager System for Distributed Computing Infrastructure

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Abstract—As the use of science gateways and other high-level tools to run scientific workloads on Distributed Computing Infrastructure (DCI) increases, and as security threats escalate, the challenge of securely automating workflows also increases. Workflow automation requires gateways to login to hosts on behalf of users to accomplish a variety of tasks, including staging input files, submitting and monitoring jobs, archiving results, etc. Authenticating to these hosts requires managing credentials, and, increasingly, providing interactive responses to multi-factor authentication (MFA) challenges. Automating the authentication process presents challenges and raises security concerns.

In this paper, we introduce the Trust Manager System (TMS), an open-source cyberinfrastructure designed to address the above challenges by providing secure automated workflows for credential management and remote host authentication. TMS supports MFA with no-human-in-the-loop *most of the time* as well as SSH keypairs and tokens that may be short-lived or one-time use. TMS includes a suite of *host modules*, installed directly on DCI, together with *TMS Server*, a system providing API and web-based flows that coordinate and manage trust between users, third-party applications, and DCI. TMS protocols build on well-known open standards such as OAuth2 and OIDC. We present the design and initial implementation of TMS, descriptions of early adoption from its deployment at the Texas Advanced Computing Center, as well as a set of future directions for the platform.

Keywords—security, credential management, workflow automation, MFA

I. INTRODUCTION

Scientific workflows executed on Distributed Computing Infrastructure (DCI) often run for extended periods and access resources from different service providers, including academic computing centers and commercial clouds. For example, consider a science gateway that stages input files from an AWS S3 bucket to a High Performance Computing (HPC) system, runs a workload, monitors its progress, then archives the output to a high-capacity storage system. Two main challenges in automating such a workflow are to (1) securely manage user credentials, and (2) authenticate without human intervention. Significant impediments to automation include restrictions on sharing credentials and, increasingly, the requirement for human-in-the-loop multi-factor authentication (MFA) challenges. MFA, while an effective way to increase security, limits the level of automation that can be implemented.

To address these challenges, we designed the Trust Manager System (TMS), a framework to provide automated credential

management and authentication that enables applications to connect to host systems on behalf of users and issue commands as those users. The goals for automated application authentication under TMS are:

- No manual key distribution to individual components of the DCI
- No-human-in-the-loop MFA *most of the time*, i.e., with a policy-defined duration
- No user secrets shared with applications
- Account access using federated identities

To accomplish these goals, TMS incorporates a set of *host modules* that are installed and configured by system administrators of DCI as well as *TMS Server*, a web-based application that manages trust between users, applications, and accounts on DCI. TMS defines *flows* enabling: 1) users to establish ownership (or linking) of accounts on DCI hosts with TMS Server; 2) users to delegate to clients, such as science gateways, access to DCI host accounts that they have established ownership of; and 3) clients to generate credentials with TMS server that will be honored by DCI hosts. These credentials can be short-lived, even one-time use, and can also be used for MFA challenges.

We have deployed an initial implementation of TMS, including TMS Server and a host module, at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) and have integrated it into the Tapis API framework [1] for workflow automation. As a result, more than a dozen science gateways now leverage TMS via Tapis for automated credential management across multiple advanced computing clusters deployed at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) at the University of Texas, Austin.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: in Section II, we motivate the work with background on automated workflows, authentication with DCI and the associated challenges. In Section III, we provide a detailed description of the TMS design and in Section IV we describe our initial implementation of TMS and early adopters of our first deployment at TACC. Finally, in Section V, we conclude with our plans for future work.

II. MOTIVATION AND BACKGROUND

Some of the challenges described in this paper are addressed by existing efforts, such as EGI Check-In [2], CILogon [3] and

Globus [4]. However, these projects do not address several of the difficult challenges that are addressed by TMS, including:

- automated secure generation and distribution of credentials for remote resources, including proof of ownership for user accounts on the resources
- support for no-human-in-the-loop MFA most of the time, with policy driven restrictions

A. Automated Workflows

Computationally intensive research workflows can span the cyberinfrastructure (CI) of multiple commercial, academic and governmental facilities. These facilities represent distinct physical, geographic and administrative domains. While cross institutional processing brings more resources to bear on a problem, it also increases the complexity of workload management and security.

Case in point are climatology studies which often require multi-step analyses. The first step aggregates data collected in real-time by sensors on weather stations and begins analysis near collection points. If outliers are detected, a second simulation step is triggered to produce a high-precision forecast. Some simulations, such as those based on Lagrangian Particle Tracking [5], require high-performance computing resources far from weather stations. Adhering to the security policies of multiple institutions and managing multiple credentials and authorizations is difficult enough, but when human-in-the-loop MFA is introduced, special accommodation is required to automate workflows. Even within a single site, these accommodations can involve cooperation between the networking, security and application development departments.

Cloud frameworks for research computing, such as Globus [6], OnDemand [7], and Tapis [1], which provide programmable interfaces to automate computational tasks, are not immune to these challenges. For instance, at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC), a subset of Tapis components have been authorized to run on MFA-exempt nodes. These designated components can access other TACC resources without human intervention, but this is only because compensating security measures have been put in place. When the Ohio Supercomputer Center (OSC) recently introduced MFA, Tapis running at TACC could no longer access OSC systems on which users previously ran jobs.

The TMS approach is to pre-configure authenticated pathways to resources that allow application access without human intervention most of the time. Occasionally, and in accordance with site policies, these pre-configured pathways will require re-authentication, typically with MFA. Well-defined TMS interfaces can alert applications when re-authentication is necessary and allow them to inform users on how to proceed.

B. Multimodal Authentication

Each data center supports remote login in its own way. Most allow SSH login, but the manner in which passwords, keys and certificates are used is set by local policy. MFA adds extra protection, but again, different institutions employ different implementations. In addition, new authentication methods are

constantly being developed, including methods that use biometrics, tokens and physical devices. Incorporating them into TMS is an important goal.

Given that no one size fits all, TMS is conceived as a modular technology platform where different authentication protocols can share common implementation technologies, development processes, management interfaces and deployment scripts. The design supports an extensible infrastructure into which new login methodologies can be added or customized.

C. Reusable Programmable Agent

Cloud frameworks such as Tapis use a *zero-install* approach to execute commands on remote hosts. That is, these applications use SSH to login to hosts with credentials previously provided by users, which means no application code is installed on the target hosts. This approach generally works well, though some users and institutions are unwilling to share account credentials with a remote application. The downside is that sharing complicates secrets management and offers another place where secrets are vulnerable to exploits.

To address these issues, the TMS design supports an HTTPS agent that accepts well-defined requests from one or more applications. Each request will execute a command under a specified user's account. Just like SSH, the agent runs with elevated privileges, though it will use an interface definition language (IDL) to precisely define and limit each application's requests and parameters, allowing the agent to automatically validate command input before executing it. The TMS agent can be configurable for any number of applications, making it a reusable HTTPS agent that saves each application from writing, deploying and securing their own individual remote agents. The agent can be deployed separately from the rest of TMS.

There is precedent for installing remote agents on HPC systems. Examples include the transfer application Globus [8] and the Open OnDemand platform [9]. HPC centers typically have a process for reviewing and approving such agents.

III. DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we present the design and architecture of TMS. Broadly speaking, TMS provides two sets of functions: first, functionalities focused on enabling users to link accounts on different DCI hosts and to delegate authorization to clients to take action on their behalf using those accounts; and second, functionalities focused on enabling clients to actually authenticate and execute commands on remote DCI hosts on behalf of users.

The physical architecture of TMS comprises two sets of components that integrate together to provide the functions described above. *TMS host modules*, which are programs installed directly onto DCI hosts and which provide support for account linking, authentication and command execution; and *TMS Server*, a lightweight HTTP server deployed on commodity cloud infrastructure that manages trust relationships between users, accounts and clients, and provides flows for generating credentials that can be used by clients on DCI hosts.

Fig. 1. TMS Architecture

TMS utilizes a set of OAuth2 [10] style *flows* for the following tasks: 1) Linking users to host accounts that they own, 2) delegating authorization to client applications for host accounts owned by users, and 3) generating credentials by clients that have been delegated authorization. Host modules coordinate with TMS server to support these flows. Additionally, host modules support the validation of credentials presented by client applications and the ability to execute remote commands on the DCI host where they are installed.

In the following subsections, we describe components of TMS organized into the high-level functions that they support.

A. Executing Commands on Remote Hosts

As shown in the architecture diagram in Figure 1, the TMS server has a REST API front-end configured with:

- a Time-based One Time Password (TOTP) authenticator that allows applications to programmatically satisfy MFA challenges
- an SSH key pair generator
- a token generator
- a database to persist data

TMS is not itself an Identity Provider (IDP), but instead will interact with existing federated (e.g., InCommon [11], EGI [12]) and institution-specific IDPs (e.g., LDAP, Active Directory).

The diagram shows how various TMS components are deployed on the target host systems. The command line program **tmsctl** is used to communicate with the TMS server during an account linking flow (see III-B1). Associated with **tmsctl** is the TMS **HostSigner** daemon that provides a secure way to (1) identify the user account and host running **tmsctl** and (2) guarantee the integrity of data transmitted from **tmsctl** to the TMS server. Hosts that support generated SSH keys will

Fig. 2. Flow showing TMS authorizing an application for remote access

need SSHD to be configured with the TMS **KeyCmd** program to dynamically retrieve public keys from the TMS server. Hosts that support token login will need a custom Pluggable Authentication Modules (PAM) [13] module installed to parse and validate tokens. This PAM module may be adapted from an existing implementation, such as SciTokens [14], or may need to be built from scratch. Hosts that support non-SSH based application authentication will need the TMS Agent installed.

The WebAuthn component is included as an example of how TMS can be extended to explore other authentication methods. WebAuthn [15] is a web standard for public key authentication. It is resistant to phishing, replay, and credential theft attacks and can operate on many types of portable authentication devices. Although supported by all major browsers, WebAuthn adoption in research CI is limited by the lack of client capabilities in non-web environments. This challenge can be addressed by building WebAuthn architectural components in Rust, such as the relying party interface, which will allow login to CI resources like storage, HPC, HTC, and cloud systems. For example, there are existing Rust libraries for WebAuthn [16].

1) Authentication Flow using a one-time SSH keypair:

Figure 2 illustrates how a TMS-enabled application uses a one-time SSH keypair to login to user accounts.

The flow assumes that the application has been registered with TMS and that the user has (1) linked an identity to Host A, (2) delegated access to Host A to the application using that identity, and (3) registered with the TMS TOTP module. These actions are all supported by TMS interfaces. The linking and delegating flows are discussed in the sections below.

In step 1, the user makes a request that requires the application to login to Host A. In step 2, the application requests a one-time use SSH keypair from TMS. Included in the step 2 request is the application's client secret, the user identity and the target host. TMS validates the client secret, checks that the host account has been linked to the user's identity, checks that the application has been delegated access to the host account, and checks that the user's MFA has not expired. If all checks pass, TMS generates a keypair, storing the public key in its database and passing the private key to the application. In step 3, the application attempts to login to the user's account on Host A using the private key. In step 4, SSHD calls the configured **KeyCmd** module which retrieves the user's public key from TMS. Because this is a one-time keypair, TMS then deletes the public key. If it were not a one-time keypair, TMS would delete the public key if it had expired or reached the limit for number of uses. In step 5, SSHD sends an MFA challenge back to the application. In step 6, the application requests an MFA pass code, which includes the application's client secret, user identity and target host. TMS validates the input as before and returns the code generated by the TOTP module. The application passes the code to SSHD completing step 5 and the login. The application can now run commands under the user's account.

Token-based flows will follow the same control flow as SSH keys, except that tokens will be created by TMS and validated on hosts using a PAM module. Tokens typically will be JSON Web Tokens (JWTs) [17], such as SciTokens [14]. As discussed in the next section, use of JWTs allow for tokens containing authorization claims that can be used for scoping login sessions.

2) *Non-SSH Based Authentication*: In the design, although not yet implemented, a programmable TMS Agent acts as an on-host proxy for applications to run Linux commands. The Agent runs with elevated privileges, such as the POSIX CAP SETUID and CAP SETGID capabilities. This allows it to execute commands with an effective UID of any unprivileged (non-root) user. Applications connect via HTTPS rather than SSH and use tokens or keys to authenticate with the Agent. A JSON schema based on an interface definition language (IDL) allows each application to precisely define its Agent interface, which can support standard application/json REST requests as well as file upload and download. The IDL's built-in functions and expression language enable automatic command validation that rarely requires custom input checking code. The Agent can be written in Rust using a plugin architecture allowing external command processors to be written in any language for prototyping and fast development. The result is a universal command proxy with secure access and precisely defined interfaces that can be run independently of the rest of TMS.

As mentioned above, the use of JWTs for token-based flows allows for the integration of operating system authorization checking for host logins. TMS can generate tokens containing authorization claims, allowing login sessions to be scoped. For example, the user could include a read-only scope when delegating authority.

Fig. 3. Host account linking

B. Linking Accounts and Delegating Authorization

A key distinction must be made between *accounts* on DCI hosts and *users*, which have identities at universities, academic computing centers, commercial cloud platforms and other institutions. While distinct, these entities are linked by the fact that individual users own and are responsible for host accounts. Linking host accounts to users identities is thus of fundamental importance.

1) *Linking User Identity to User Host Account*: The TMS design includes a protocol to link a user's identity to host login accounts such that applications using TMS can access those hosts and meet the automation goals set forth in the Introduction. The protocol embeds an OAuth2 flow in a TMS flow.

The sequence diagram in figure 3 depicts the five step process that allows users to link cloud (i.e., external) identities to host accounts. In step 1, a user begins by logging into their host and issuing a call to **tmstcl** to initiate the account linking protocol. In step 2, **tmstcl** assembles the request information, which includes the host and user account, gets it signed by the **HostSigner** as discussed above, and sends it in a REST call to the TMS server. TMS returns a unique URL that is passed back to the user. In step 3, the user navigates to the URL in a browser and is redirected by TMS to select an IDP and complete an OAuth2 OIDC authorization flow. This flow returns an identity (i.e., username) that TMS stores. TMS generates and returns a device code to the user. In step 4, the user passes the device code to **tmstcl** on the original host to finalize account linkage. In step 5, **tmstcl** sends a finalize request containing the host, user and device code to TMS, which validates the information and completes the mapping from user identity to the host account.

By logging on to the host, the user proves their account

Fig. 4. Account access delegation

access bona fides. By running `tmsctl`, the user ties TMS authorization to an OAuth2 flow which links an identity to the account. The following TMS/OAuth2 flow allows an identified user to delegate host access to an application.

2) *Delegating Account Access to Applications*: Given that a user has linked a cloud identity to a host account as discussed in the previous section, the sequence diagram in figure 4 depicts the two step process that allows the user to delegate access to an application. In step 1, the user initiates an application defined delegation procedure. The `parms1` parameters specify the user, client application, host account, allowed authentication methods, delegation time-to-live, number of uses and any required MFA information. The application validates, finalizes and passes these parameters to the TMS server. TMS validates the client and user/host linkage, records the information and returns a delegation code and URL. The code and URL are then passed back to the user. In step 2, the user visits the URL in a browser, provides the delegation code and is then redirected to complete an OAuth2 OIDC authorization flow to verify their identity. Upon success, TMS activates the delegation, which allows the application to login to the host account using the user’s linked identity.

IV. INITIAL IMPLEMENTATION AND EARLY ADOPTERS

We implemented an initial version of TMS server as well as a KeyCmd host module in the Rust programming language [18]. We licensed all source code via a permissive BSD-3 clause open-source license [19] and it is available on GitHub [20]. We chose Rust for its safety and performance features, as well as for compile-time race condition detection, memory safety and other code integrity features [21][22][23]. We deployed a production instance of TMS server at TACC, and the TMS KeyCmd module has been installed on multiple HPC clusters at TACC, including Vista, Lonestar6, and the Corral high-performance storage system.

Additionally, we extended various Tapis APIs, including the Tapis Systems service [24], to support authentication and access via TMS. Specifically, Tapis Systems now support an authentication method of `TMS_KEYS`, enabling users to

register DCI hosts configured to honor credentials issued by the production TMS server installation. With this method, users may define a Tapis system using `TMS_KEYS` and use it to manage files, submit jobs, and other tasks, without ever having to explicitly provide Tapis with a credential to the system.

As a result, more than a dozen science gateway projects currently leverage TMS for access to TACC hosts. The projects include include NeuroNex [25], 3DEM gateway for 3D Electron Microscopy [26], the DesignSafe portal [27], a natural hazards engineering CI, and MATCSSI [28], a gateway for many-body electronic structure calculations.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we described common challenges faced by science gateways and other applications when automating workflows on distributed computing infrastructure (DCI), and we presented the Trust Manager System (TMS), a project aiming to address these challenges by providing web-friendly protocols for delegating authorization to and invoking commands on remote DCI hosts. We reviewed the TMS design and initial implementation, as well as an initial deployment at the Texas Advanced Computing Center. We also discussed an integration of TMS into the Tapis API framework and its initial usage in several science gateways.

In the near future, we plan to implement additional TMS server functionality and host modules, including support for TOTP/MFA and for issuing and honoring tokens formatted as JWTs. A TMS deployment at the San Diego Supercomputer Center (SDSC) is also planned. In the longer term, we envision supporting new protocols showing promise but not yet receiving full adoption in the science gateway community, such as WebAuthn.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation Office of Advanced CyberInfrastructure: specifically, the Tapis Framework [1931439 and 1931575], the ICICLE AI Insitute [2112606], and SGX3 [2231406].

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